

Studies in the Optical Properties of Chlorophyll. Part I. Absorption of Light by Solutions and Suspensions of Chlorophyll- α and Chlorophyll- β and their Mixtures.

By J. C. GHOSH AND SUNIL BEHARI SEN-GUPTA.

The absorption spectra of solutions of chlorophyll have been examined qualitatively by a large number of investigators. The spectragrams obtained by Wilstätter and Stoll show that solutions of chlorophyll- α have seven sharply defined absorption bands in the visible, of which the three strong bands are in the red, indigo blue and violet with band heads at about $660\mu\mu$, $460\mu\mu$, and $430\mu\mu$. The absorption spectra of chlorophyll- β solutions show nine bands in the visible, of which the strongest have band heads at about $640\mu\mu$, $455\mu\mu$ and $430\mu\mu$.

Tsvett (*Ber. Deut. bot. Ges.*, 1907, **25**, 388; *ibid.*, 1918, **36**, 74; *Z. wiss. Mikrosk.*, 1888, **5**, 289), and Warburg and Nigelein (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1923, **106**, 195), determined the extinction coefficients of chlorophyll solutions quantitatively by spectrophotometric methods, but evidently they did not use absolutely pure samples of chlorophyll. Thus Warburg and Nigelein extracted the pigments from the *algae chlorella* and determined the extinction coefficient for a solution of 0.2 g. of dry pigment, which contained both chlorophyll- α and- β in 1000 c.c. of solution by the König-Marten spectrophotometer.

In this paper, measurements of extinction coefficients of pure samples of chlorophyll- α and chlorophyll- β and also their mixtures in states of solution and suspension will be described. The results obtained enable us to calculate the total chlorophyll content in a sample of a liquid and also the ratio of chlorophyll- α to- β .

EXPERIMENTAL.

Pure samples of chlorophyll- α and chlorophyll- β were very kindly prepared for the purpose of this investigation by Prof. Stoll. Both chlorophyll- α and- β dissolve in acetone to form molecularly disperse

solutions. Suspensions of chlorophyll in water containing 1% acetone were prepared by dissolving the required quantity of chlorophyll in one c. c. of acetone and adding 99 c. c. of water.

Emulsions of chlorophyll in water were prepared with the help of lecithin as follows:—Chlorophyll was dissolved in absolute alcohol, while lecithin was dissolved in alcohol-ether mixtures in the ratio of 5:1. The two solutions were mixed together and the requisite quantity of pure water was added. The suspension was dialysed for 3 weeks in a stream of pure water, with the addition of chloroform to prevent the growth of the fungus. The dialysed suspension did not contain alcohol or ether. Many plant physiologists are of opinion that the chlorophyll in plant leaves exists in a state of true solution in lipoid bodies, which in their turn remain suspended in aqueous medium as fine colloidal particles. Suspension of chlorophyll in water containing lecithin may in a sense be considered to have similar optical properties to those of chloroplasts in the plant leaves.

For the determination of the extinction coefficients, a König-Marten spectrophotometer was used. The wave-length scale of the apparatus was calibrated by the lines from a mercury lamp. A rectangular double absorption glass cell, with chlorophyll solution in one chamber and pure water in the other, was placed on the spectrometer table and the molar extinction coefficient was calculated from the equation

$$\epsilon = \frac{\log \tan A - \log \tan A'}{c \cdot d},$$

where, c denotes the molar concentration of chlorophyll in solution and suspension and d , the thickness of the cell, expressed in millimeters and A and A' are respectively the final and initial angles.

The thickness of the solution was 1 cm. and the strength of chlorophyll solution or emulsion never exceeded $M/20,000$. The concentration of lecithin used did not exceed $M/20,000$. Lecithin was purified according to the directions of Levene and Rolf (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1927, 72, 587).

The experimental data are recorded in Tables I, II, III and are represented graphically in Figs. 1, 2, 3, respectively. The molecular extinction coefficients given below are to be multiplied by 10^4 and are given in the following tables against the corresponding wave-lengths.

TABLE I.

Chlorophyll- α and- β and their mixtures in acetone solutions.

Wave length.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
	100 p.c. (α)	90 p.c. 10 p.c.	80 p.c. 20 p.c.	70 p.c. 30 p.c.	60 p.c. 40 p.c.	50 p.c. 50 p.c.	40 p.c. 60 p.c.	30 p.c. 70 p.c.	20 p.c. 80 p.c.	10 p.c. 90 p.c.	100 p.c. (β)
6900	·0153	·0153	·0153	·0153	·0153	·0142	·0142	·0142	·0142	·0142	·0106
6800	·0395	·0374	·0350	·0332	·0332	·0311	·0258	·0258	·0226	·0205	·0184
6700	·0850	·0800	·0760	·0760	·0635	·0592	·0544	·0502	·0452	·0412	·0350
6600	·1423	·1355	·1277	·1186	·1107	·1022	·0944	·0866	·0800	·0713	·0635
6500	·0920	·0920	·0920	·0920	·0920	·0920	·0920	·0920	·0920	·0920	·0940
6400	·0544	·0584	·0615	·0650	·0688	·0702	·0755	·0800	·0828	·0870	·0900
6300	·0452	·0472	·0472	·0500	·0500	·0525	·0525	·0550	·0550	·0550	·0600
6200	·0427	·0427	·0427	·0427	·0427	·0427	·0427	·0427	·0427	·0427	·0430
6100	·0412	·0412	·0412	·0412	·0412	·0412	·0412	·0412	·0412	·0412	·0412
6000	·0345	·0345	·0345	·0345	·0374	·0374	·0374	·0374	·0374	·0395	·0395
4800	·0147	·0230	·0300	·0387	·0464	·0611	·0624	·0700	·0787	·0661	·0940
4700	·0147	·0390	·0600	·0820	·1034	·1245	·1451	·1675	·1895	·2165	·2316
4600	·0345	·0619	·0900	·1168	·1400	·1884	·2000	·2264	·2540	·2810	·3087
4400	·1320	·1472	·1624	·1775	·1925	·2125	·2240	·2382	·2540	·2700	·2838
4350	·2199	·2250	·2321	·2321	·2400	·2420	·2440	·2500	·2600	·2722	·2756

TABLE III.

*Molecular extinction coefficient of chlorophyll- α and- β emulsions and their mixtures in
M/32000 lecithin (after dialysis).*

Wave-length	1 100 p.c. (α)	2 90 p.c. 10 p.c.	3 80 p.c. 20 p.c.	4 70 p.c. 30 p.c.	5 60 p.c. 40 p.c.	6 50 p.c. 50 p.c.	7 40 p.c. 60 p.c.	8 30 p.c. 70 p.c.	9 20 p.c. 80 p.c.	10 10 p.c. 90 p.c.	11 100 p.c. (β)
6900	·0447	·0424	·0400	·0378	·0353	·0330	·0307	·0307	·0271	·0238	·0218
6800	·0632	·0600	·0567	·0535	·0500	·0480	·044	·0400	·0375	·0343	·0311
6700	·0757	·0717	·0688	·0653	·0620	·0600	·055	·0510	·0480	·0446	·0412
6600	·0652	·0652	·0630	·0630	·0608	·0584	·0584	·0570	·0570	·0544	·0554
6500	·0447	·0447	·0447	·0447	·0447	·0471	·0471	·0500	·0500	·0500	·0540
6400	·0311	·0330	·0360	·0371	·0386	·0433	·0451	·0462	·0480	·0480	·0500
6300	·0280	·0280	·0280	·0280	·0307	·0320	·0320	·0320	·0350	·0350	·0380
6200	·0280	·0280	·0280	·0280	·029	·0290	·0290	·0290	·0330	·0330	·0330
6100	·0215	·0225	·0225	·0243	·0243	·0256	·0256	·0271	·0271	·0311	·0311
6000	·0170	·0182	·0200	·0200	·0220	·0220	·0256	·0256	·0285	·0285	·0285
4900	·0311	·0360	·0400	·0457	·0500	·0551	·0602	·0653	·0705	·0757	·0800
4800	·0311	·0810	·0452	·0521	·0600	·0665	·0734	·0800	·0875	·0945	·1016
4600	·0361	·0500	·0633	·0770	·0900	·1043	·1177	·1221	·1450	·1600	·1722
4400	·0600	·0712	·0825	·0930	1044	·1162	·1226	·1375	·1500	·1600	·1722
4350	·1068	·1150	·1200	·1250	·1300	·1351	·1450	·1498	·1585	·1700	·1800

Similar experiment was done with the same results in M/2000 lecithin.

TABLE IV.

Chlorophyll- α emulsion in lecithin.

Concentration of lecithin.

Wave-length.	M/2000	M/4000	M/8000	M/16000	M/32000
6900	·0437	·0437	·0457	·0437	·0447
6800	·0620	·0620	·0620	·0620	·0632
6700	·0734	·0734	·0756	·0756	·0756
6600	·0627	·0627	·0627	·0627	·0630
6500	·0447	·0147	·0447	·0447	·0447
6400	·0311	·0311	·0311	·0311	·0311
6300	·0280	·0280	·0280	·0280	·0280
6100	·0215	·0215	·0215	·0215	·0215
6000	·0180	·0180	·0180	·0180	·0180
4900	·0311	·0311	·0311	·0311	·0311
4600	·0361	·0361	·0361	·0361	·0361
4400	·0600	·0600	·0600	·0600	·0600
4350	·1120	·1120	·1068	·1068	·1068

TABLE V.

Chlorophyll- β emulsion in lecithin.

Concentration of lecithin.

Wave-length.	M/2000	M/4000	M/8000	M/16000	M/32000
6900	·0220	·0215	·0215	·0215	·0218
6800	·0307	·0307	·0307	·0307	·0311
6700	·0412	·0412	·0412	·0412	0412
6600	·0544	·0544	·0544	·0544	·0544
6400	·0471	·0471	·0500	·0500	·0500
6300	·0380	·0380	·0380	·0380	·0380
6200	·0330	·0330	·0330	·0330	·0330
6100	·0311	·0311	·0311	·0311	·0311
6000	·0265	·0265	·0265	·0265	·0285
4900	·0800	·0800	·0800	·0800	·0800
4800	·1016	·1016	·1016	·1016	·1016
4700	·1400	·1400	·1400	·1374	·1374
4600	·1722	·1722	·1722	·1722	·1722
4400	·1800	·1800	·1780	·1780	·1780
4350	·1930	·1930	·1850	·1800	·1800

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

It will be seen that, as a general rule, in all solutions of suspensions, chlorophyll- α has a larger extinction coefficient than that of chlorophyll- β for wave-lengths larger than $6400 \text{ \AA}$ — $6300 \text{ \AA}$, whereas for smaller wave-lengths, the extinction coefficients of chlorophyll- β become larger than that of chlorophyll- α .

In Fig. 1, the molecular extinction coefficients of acetone solutions of chlorophyll- α and- β , and their mixtures are represented. The molar concentration of any chlorophyll- $(\alpha + \beta)$ solution in acetone can at once be found by observing the extinction coefficient ϵ' , which is expressed by $\epsilon' = \frac{\log \tan A - \log \tan A'}{d}$ at $\lambda = 6500 \text{ \AA}$, where curves from 1 to 11 meet, and dividing the molar extinction coefficient ϵ by ϵ' .

The total chlorophyll concentration being known, the ratio of chlorophyll- α : chlorophyll- β can be ascertained by finding out the molar extinction coefficient at $\lambda = 4600 \text{ \AA}$, where for small changes in the ratio of chlorophyll- α : - β , there is a large change in the value of the molecular extinction coefficient. Thus a molar extinction coefficient of chlorophyll- $(\alpha + \beta)$ represented by the point X (8) in

Fig. 1 can be shown by graphical interpolation to have the $\alpha : \beta$ ratio = 3:7.

What is true of acetone solutions of chlorophyll is also true of chlorophyll suspensions. Only the wave-lengths where chlorophyll- α and chlorophyll- β have identical values of molecular extinction coefficients are shifted more towards the red. For these suspensions also, the molecular concentration of chlorophyll- $(\alpha + \beta)$ and also of the ratio of α/β can be calculated from extinction coefficient data in precisely the same way as in acetone solutions.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY OF DACCA.

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